

A MULTILEVEL FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF A TEXTILE COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY

The textile composite studied is a multi-scale material. A representative volume element is defined by a periodic cell of the material. Parallel finite element computations are performed in order to compare macroscopic response with experimental one and then to access the local heterogeneous stress/strain fields.

Keywords: Textile composite; Finite elements; meso-modelling; multilevel analysis

INTRODUCTION AND AIM OF THE STUDY

Textile composite materials are found to be increasing in numerous industrial applications like automotive, aeronautic, aerospace,... In fact, they offer remarkable material properties (high strength, light weight) and facilities and a low cost to process final products.

However, because of their complex three-dimensionnal microstructures, the prediction of their effective properties and the access of local fields is difficult. Several simplified analytical models were proposed [18, 19, 20, 23, 22]. These models give an estimate of elastic properties of composite material. They require to know the behaviour of the different components and the geometry of the woven fabric. But when the geometry of this woven fabric is too complex, these models are too simple to correctly predict the properties of composite. So, during the last decade, multiscale analysis methods (localization/ homogenization) have been developed associated to Finite Elements Method (FEM). These numerical methods give a best estimate of global properties of material and the possibility to access the local heterogeneous stress/strain fields [14, 6]. In fact, the textile composite structure (supposed to be periodic) is precisely discretized in a representative cell of a Representative volume element (RVE).

Nevertheless, until now, the composites studied are n-harness satin with $n < 5$ [13]. The number of degree of freedom must be lower than 200000. In this case, the resolution of problems can be made on sequential calculators because it requires a memory, a disk space and a computing time compatible with these calculators. In this paper, we analyze a three dimensionnal textile composite whose the periodic pattern has a number of degrees of freedom of 1 322 079. Therefore, it is necessary to use numerical techniques like the decomposition into a set of sub-domains and the parallel computation.

Moreover, the behaviour of components (fibres and matrix) is usually considered as linear elastic whereas the non-linearities observed at the macroscopic scale can be important. They generally have two distinct origins : a geometric origins because the orientation of yarns are modified, induced by straining [9], and a material origin due to non-linear behaviour of the components, in particular the increasing of thermoplastic fibres' stiffness. Few authors have studied the non-linear behaviour of the components [1, 15, 16, 17, 4, 5]. In this paper, we study the influence of these two non-linear sources about the macroscopic behaviour of the composite material, associated with a great textile microstructure.

To predict the effective properties of composite materials and to analyse the local phenomena (damage, cracking), multiscale analysis methods (localization/homogenization) have been developed associated with FEM. These methods requires the knowledge of the constituents' behaviour.

PRESENTATION OF THE MATERIAL

MATERIAL'S MICROSTRUCTURE

The composite studied in this paper is a three dimensional textile (supposed to be periodic) embedded in a PVC matrix of which thickness is 9 mm. The textile is composed of PET fibres for the warp yarns and PA66 fibres and cotton fibres for the weft yarns. The woven microstructure has been identified with transverse sections of the composite using optical microscope. The textile composite has three principal levels of organization : at the macroscopic scale, the composite can be considered as an orthotropic homogeneous continuous material (at first approximation). The mesoscopic scale allows to take the geometry of fabric into account but the yarns are considered to be orthotropic continued materials. The representative cell of RVE corresponds then to that identified with the microscopic observations. In this paper, interest is focused on mesoscopic key scale and its implications on macroscopic scale. So, the transition between the mesoscopic and the macroscopic scales is studied.

Figure 1: Transverse cutting of the textile composite.

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF THE COMPONENTS

The behaviour of the components (yarns and matrix) was reported elsewhere [24] . We thus lay out for this study :

- transverse isotropic behaviour of yarns. In this paper, we neglect the variations of yarns properties induced by their own strain [2, 10].
- isotropic behaviour of the matrix.

Several cases can be considered. First, a first calculation is carried out by regarding the behaviour of all the components (yarns and matrix) as isotropic linear elastic [24] . The second case consists of linear elastic behaviour of components but taking into account transverse isotropic behaviour of yarns. The transversal moduli and the shear moduli are obtained by inverse method with mechanical test carried out on the composite [24]. These moduli are smaller than longitudinal modulus of yarns because of their fibrous structure. Finally the case which takes into account the non-linear behaviour of yarns is considered.

The increasing of stiffness observed during the monotonous tensile tests was modelled with an elastoplastic behaviour with two isotropic hardenings. The threshold function is :

$$f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, R) = J(\boldsymbol{\sigma}) - R \quad (1)$$

with R is a scalar variable defining the isotropic hardening of material such as :

$$R = R_0 + Q(1 - e^{-bp}) + A(e^{Bp} - 1) \quad (2)$$

with p cumulated plastic strain, and R_0 , Q , b , A and B material parameters to be determined. These five parameters are obtained thanks to optimization techniques from the results of tensile tests carried out on yarns.

The undulation of yarns in the textile, as well as the variation of these undulations, require to correctly take into account their anisotropic behaviour. More precisely, if a strain is applied in the direction of warp of fabric, the warp yarns have tendency to align parallel to direction of strain while undulation of weft yarns increases [2]. Mechanical characteristics of yarns in the reference bench mark of the cell must be regularly updated using the local bench mark update in which these characteristics are expressed. To do this, in each point of the medium fibre of each yarn, the angle of the tangent of this medium fibre between its current configuration and its initial configuration, was calculated. This angle, estimated to be the only one which evolves among the three Euler's angles which define the rotation of the local bench mark in the reference bench mark, was thus updated with each increment of calculation. It should be specified that this updating of rotation is not that exact of the material which is indentified during the construction of kinematics of a continious medium in finite strains.

MULTISCALE MODELLING

OBJECTIVES OF THE MULTISCALE MODELLING

The multiscale procedure achieves the transition between the macroscopic scale and the mesoscopic scale. The effective behaviour (macroscopic) is determined by the homogenization knowing the fabric geometry, its evolution and the components behaviour. The local stress/strain fields is determined by the localization. This method allows a better understanding of the local damage mechanisms. Indeed, the damage is not controlled by the mean value of stresses or strains but by values locally reached [8] (important stress/strain concentrations induced by the undulations).

PERIODIC HOMOGENIZATION

For a periodic material, the microscopic displacement writes as the sum of a periodic field and a macroscopic field :

$$\underline{u}(\underline{x}) = \underline{v}(\underline{x}) + \epsilon_{ij}^{\mu+1} . \underline{x} \quad (3)$$

where \underline{v} is periodic, i.e. \underline{v} have the same values on the opposite sides of the periodic cell, \underline{x} is the local coordonate and $\epsilon_{ij}^{\mu+1}$ is the infinitesimal strain tensor defined on the global length scale. To perform a FE computation, the nodes of the periodic cell's side must be in the same position in the opposite side. The meshing of opposite sides must be the same.

Consider an object which is statistically homogeneous at the global scale but heterogeneous at the microscopic scale. At the macroscopic scale, the equations of the mechanical problems are [7] :

$$\sigma_{ij}^{\mu+1} + \rho^{\mu+1} b_i^{\mu+1} = 0 \text{ in } V^{\mu+1} \quad (4)$$

where the superscript $\mu + 1$ stands for the global length scale, $\sigma_{ij}^{\mu+1}$ is the Cauchy stress tensor, $\rho^{\mu+1}$ is the mass density of the homogeneous object, $b_i^{\mu+1}$ is the body force vector per unit mass and $V^{\mu+1}$ is the volume of the object at the macroscopic scale.

$$\sigma_{ij}^{\mu+1} = \sigma_{ji}^{\mu+1} \text{ in } V^{\mu+1} \quad (5)$$

$$\epsilon_{ij}^{\mu+1} = \frac{1}{2}(u_{i,j}^{\mu+1} + u_{j,i}^{\mu+1}) \text{ in } V^{\mu+1} \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma_{ij}^{\mu+1}(t) = \Omega_{\tau=\infty}^{\tau=t} \{ \epsilon_{ij}^{\mu+1}(\tau) \} \text{ in } V^{\mu+1} \quad (7)$$

where $\Omega_{\tau=\infty}^{\tau=t} \{ \epsilon_{ij}^{\mu+1} \}$ is a functional mapping that accounts for history dependent effects, such as viscoelasticity, and is determined from the locally averaged constitutive behaviour.

If appropriate initial and boundary conditions are added to these equations, the problem is well posed. Moreover, the different scale must respect this inequality :

$$d \ll l^\mu \ll l^{\mu+1}, l_\omega^{\mu+1} \quad (8)$$

where d is the heterogeneities scale, l^μ is the cell periodic scale, $l^{\mu+1}$ is the global length scale and $l_\omega^{\mu+1}$ is the length of the wave propagating on the global scale.

At the global scale, the equations of the problem are :

$$\sigma_{ij}^\mu + \rho^\mu b_i^\mu = 0 \text{ in } V^\mu \quad (9)$$

where the superscript μ stands for the local length scale.

$$\sigma_{ij}^\mu = \sigma_{ji}^\mu \text{ in } V^\mu \quad (10)$$

$$\epsilon_{ij}^\mu = \frac{1}{2}(u_{i,j}^\mu + u_{j,i}^\mu) \text{ in } V^\mu \quad (11)$$

$$\sigma_{ij}^\mu(t) = \Omega_{\tau=-\infty}^{\tau=t} \{\epsilon_{ij}^\mu(\tau)\} \text{ in } V^\mu \quad (12)$$

where in the case of the local scale $\Omega_{\tau=-\infty}^{\tau=t} \{\epsilon_{ij}^\mu(\tau)\}$ is known a priori.

In order to complete the description of our multiscale model, we need to establish some relationships connecting both length scale.

$$\epsilon_{ij}^{\mu+1} = \bar{\epsilon}_{ij}^\mu = \frac{1}{V^\mu} \int_{V^\mu} \epsilon_{ij}^\mu dV \quad (13)$$

$$\sigma_{ij}^{\mu+1} = \bar{\sigma}_{ij}^\mu = \frac{1}{V^\mu} \int_{V^\mu} \sigma_{ij}^\mu dV \quad (14)$$

MESHING OF THE PERIODIC CELL AND PARALLEL COMPUTATION

MESHING

Because of the complexity of the fabric pattern, meshing tools developed by the Katholieke Universiteit Leuven [6, 11] has been used. Firstly, a geometric model has been created in the Wisetex software : it requires informations in particular on the pattern of fabric, the shape and the dimensions of yarns, the size of the periodic pattern. This model is then transferred into the FETex software which created a file with meshing instructions adapted to the ANSYS FE code. The meshing of the periodic cell is then performed by ANSYS. Conditions of periodicity are imposed on the different faces of the cell. The meshing obtained is then transferred toward ZeBuLoN FE code [12] developed by MINES ParisTech. Computations are carried out with the ZeBuLoN code.

Finally, the meshing consisted of tetragonal linear elements for the matrix and hexagonal and prismatic linear elements for the yarns. It consists of 440 693 nodes and 1 420 275 elements. This meshing induces an important number of degrees of freedom (1 322 079) higher than what the usual sequential computers are able to accept actually. The use of parallel computation is thus necessary.

PARALLEL COMPUTATION

There exist several methods of parallel computation. In this paper the non-overlapping domains decomposition method [21] was selected. The mesh is divided into different sub-domains and the resolution of the problem is allotted to this sub-domain with a processor. Discontinuities with the sub-domains interface is caused by each independent resolution on each sub-domain. Two methods are mainly used to treat these discontinuities : the BDD method (Balanced Domain Decomposition) and the FETI method (Finite Element Tearing and Interconnecting) [3]. The BDD method is a primal method consisting of determining displacements with the interfaces satisfying with the balance of interface. With the FETI method, the stress with the interfaces are given in order to satisfy the compatibility of displacements with the interface. It is a dual method. This method is implemented in the parallel version of ZeBuLoN code. The maximum number of degrees of freedom by processor is approximately 150 000. The meshing of the representative cell of the VER was cut out in 10 sub-domains requiring the use of 10 processors.

Figure 2: Meshing of the periodic cell (at left) and the fabric (at right).

Figure 3: Decomposition in 10 sub-domains of the periodic cell's meshing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

HOMOGENIZATION AND EFFECTIVE PROPERTIES

The effective (macroscopic) properties of the composite, are obtained with the multiscale computation. The inverse method identification allows to obtain the mechanical properties of yarns (transverse and shear behaviour). It should be noted that these data are difficult to reach experimentally.

First, the computations are carried out with the assumption of small strains in order to calculate the moduli of the composite in the warp and weft directions. We obtain a good approximation of the Young's moduli of linear elastic behaviour.

The modelling of the non-linear behaviour of the composite observed during the tensile test for the warp and weft directions is more complex. The two origins of macroscopic non-linearities were studied. The account for the variation of the undulations of yarns during the deformation of the periodic cell allowed to study the geometrical non-linearities : they induce an increasing of tangent moduli of the composite. The second origin of non linearities which is related to the non-linear behaviour of the yarns was also studied. It was taken into account while modelling the increasing of the stiffness of the yarns observed during the tensile tests with an elastoplastic behaviour (figure 4). The same type of macroscopic non-linearities has been observed during the tensile tests on the composite.

Figure 4: Macroscopic behaviour of the heterogeneous material (at left) in the warp direction and evolution of the tangent module (at right) with the imposed average strain E_{11} .

ACCESS TO THE LOCAL FIELDS

The multiscale computation has also given access to local informations. The strain/stress local fields have been calculated. Figure 5 illustrates the contour map of the stress σ_{11} in the periodic cell and in the fabric when a strain is applied in the warp direction of the material. It is the rigid phase of the composite. Moreover, heterogeneities of stresses are observed within yarns of warp. Damage initiations are likely to occur where stress concentrations are observed.

CONCLUSIONS

A procedure of multiscale analyzes of a textile composite was developed. It is held in several stages. Firstly, the woven microstructure of the composite was identified. The complexity of the pattern of fabric led to use the WiseTex Software to create the meshing of the periodic cell. The number of degrees of freedom being very high, the parallel computation was used to carry out the finite elements analysis. The constitutive equations of the components were identified with

Figure 5: Contour map of the stress σ_{11} in the periodic cell (at left) and in the fabric (at right) after apply a longitudinal strain (0,02) and with an isotropic linear behaviour for the components.

the mechanical tests but also by inverse method. The homogenization computation allowed to study the influence of origins of non-linearities on the behaviour of composite material. Finally, it was possible to access to local fields of strains and stresses within the periodic cell. Strong heterogeneities of these fields were identified within the composite. Studied local fields will allow to obtain informations on mechanisms leading to damage and fracture of the material.

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